

The Impact of Export and Import on Economic Growth in Sri Lanka

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Abstract

This study investigates the impact of exports and imports on Sri Lanka's economic growth from 1995 to 2023, using annual time series data obtained from the World Bank and other reliable sources. The analysis employs a log-linear regression model with GDP per capita as the dependent variable and exports and imports of goods and services as the independent variables. The empirical results reveal that both exports and imports have a positive relationship with economic growth in Sri Lanka. However, imports exhibit a stronger and more statistically significant effect on GDP compared to exports, suggesting that imported intermediate and capital goods play a crucial role in enhancing domestic production capacity. The high R^2 value (0.97) indicates that trade variables explain a substantial portion of GDP variation during the study period. These findings support the view that trade openness promotes growth, but also highlight the importance of the structure and composition of trade. The study concludes that while export expansion remains vital for sustainable growth, managing the quality and purpose of imports—particularly prioritizing productive over consumer imports—is essential for long-term economic stability and development in Sri Lanka.

Keywords: Economic growth, Exports, Imports, Trade, Sri Lanka, Time series analysis

Introduction

International trade and economic growth are interconnected. Trade can drive economic growth by increasing demand for a country's goods and services, expanding production, and fostering access to new technologies and resources. Sri Lanka actively engages in international trade, exporting goods and services, while importing other goods and services. In Sri Lanka, both exports and imports play a significant role in influencing economic growth, but their impacts can differ. Exports, particularly of goods and services, can drive revenue, create jobs, and increase foreign exchange reserves, boosting overall economic activity. Imports, while potentially creating a trade deficit, can also provide essential raw materials for industries, increase consumer choice, and lower prices, potentially enhancing economic welfare. Sri Lanka's central location in the Indian Ocean, bridging trade routes from the East to the West, made it a popular trading hub in ancient times, where spices, gems, and elephants were exchanged for fabrics, metals, and other goods (Jayawardena, 2011). The role of exports and imports as drivers of economic growth is rooted in classical economic theory and the Heckscher-Ohlin theory, which argues that international trade can improve the efficiency of production factors, expand markets, and increase productivity (Sukirno, 2000). Theoretically, exports can stimulate economic growth and market expansion. Additionally, exports serve as a source of foreign exchange to finance the import of

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412

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industrial raw materials and capital goods needed. This study examines the relationship between exports, imports, and economic growth in Sri Lanka. It analyzes how exports and imports contribute to Sri Lanka's economic development.

Objective of the Study

The primary objective of this study is to investigate the impact of exports and imports on Sri Lanka's economic growth. This study also aims to fill the gap in this research area in Sri Lanka

Theoretical Framework

Classical and Neoclassical theories by Adam Smith and David Ricardo emphasize comparative advantage and specialization, suggesting that trade leads to more efficient allocation of resources and economic growth. However, Endogenous Growth Theory (Romer, 1990) Suggests that trade particularly exports stimulates innovation and technology diffusion, which are essential drivers of long-term economic growth. Export-led Growth Hypothesis Argues that increasing exports contributes to GDP by expanding markets, increasing foreign exchange earnings, and enhancing productivity. Import-led Growth View: While less emphasized, some theories suggest that imports contribute to growth by providing access to cheaper inputs, capital goods, and advanced technologies.

Literature Survey

Numerous studies have been conducted in various countries, utilizing annual or panel data. Wickremasinghe, G.B. & Cameron, R. (2001) studied the Export Performance and Economic Growth in Sri Lanka. Using Granger causality and VAR models using quarterly data. This study found Bidirectional causality between exports and economic growth. Athukorala, P. & Jayasuriya, S. (2004) on their study on Macroeconomic Policies, Crises, and Growth in Sri Lanka, 1969–2000: found that Import liberalization policies had mixed impacts. While they enhanced efficiency, they also exposed the economy to external shocks and they emphasized A balanced approach to trade liberalization is needed, emphasizing export diversification Herath. & Ding, (2008) conducted a study on the Export-led Growth Hypothesis in Sri Lanka: An Empirical Investigation using time series data (1970–2005), and cointegration and Granger causality tests approach. This study found that: Exports, particularly industrial and manufactured goods, are significant drivers of Sri Lanka's GDP growth. Perera, N. & Liyanage, N. (2012) analyzed the Causal Relationship between Trade and Economic Growth in Sri Lanka using the Vector Error Correction Model (VECM), with data from 1980–2010. They found that Long-run cointegration among exports, imports, and GDP. Short-run causality flows from imports to GDP, suggesting import-led growth potential. And Both exports and imports are vital, but import quality and capital goods are key to sustained growth. Jayasinghe & Weerakoon (2017) highlighted that imports of capital goods and raw materials have a positive effect on industrial production and GDP growth. However, increasing imports of consumer goods may worsen the trade deficit. Samarasinghe (2018) found a positive long-run relationship between exports and GDP growth in Sri Lanka using time-series data from 1970 to 2016. The study supports the ELG hypothesis, particularly highlighting the role of industrial exports. Gunawardana (2019) used co-integration analysis and Granger causality tests to

show that imports of machinery and transport equipment positively influence long-term economic performance. Central Bank of Sri Lanka Annual Reports consistently point out that while essential imports support development, persistent trade deficits driven by excessive consumer imports strain foreign reserves and create macroeconomic instability. Perera & Wickramasinghe (2020) used a vector autoregressive (VAR) model and concluded that export expansion, especially in the services sector like tourism and IT, has significantly contributed to Sri Lanka's economic growth. World Bank (2021) emphasized that Sri Lanka's overdependence on a narrow set of exports such as garments and tea has limited its growth potential, recommending diversification. Millia, H. *et al.* (2021). Dissanayake and Kethmi (2021). studied the effect of exports and imports on exchange rates over short and long horizons: from Asian countries. This study includes eighteen Asian countries as the sample for and is analyzed using the Autoregressive Lag (ARDL) model. Ekanayake (2022) argues that the growing trade deficit poses challenges to sustainable growth. The study suggests that while exports contribute positively, the simultaneous rise in non-essential imports often offsets these gains. IMF Country Reports (2020–2023) indicate that a weak export base and rising import dependency contributed to Sri Lanka's balance of payments crisis, leading to foreign reserve depletion. Harningtias, (2023) also used the same methodology in their study. Another study examines the effect of exports and imports on economic growth. In Indonesia using time series data consisting of export, import, and economic growth. The test results using the autoregressive distributed lag model indicate that in the short and long run Moyo and Amoah (2024) investigated the impact of import and export on the economic growth of Ghana by using a multiple linear regression model. The variables of interest for these models were the gross domestic product representing the economic growth as the dependent variable. The authors used Import, export, and foreign direct investment populations as the independent variables in this study

From the above literature review, it is clear that the results of these empirical studies are diverse, but they generally advocate that the level of progress is an essential factor in determining the export-growth association. Moreover, the results of different studies are noticeably sensitive to the variables comprised in a relationship, the theoretical approach used, and even to the period taken and statistical and econometric methods employed.

Method and materials

The empirical analysis in this paper is based on the time series data collected in the publications of the world Bank other reliable data sets over the period from 1995 to 2023. the following estimation equation is used as a model:

$$\ln GDP_t = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \ln EX_t + \beta_2 \ln IM_t + \varepsilon_t$$

Dependent Variable is GDP per capita (current US\$): Gross domestic product is the total income earned through the production of goods and services in an economic territory during an accounting period. h. The core indicator has been divided by the general population to achieve a per capita estimate. This indicator is expressed in current price

Imports of goods and services (current US\$): Imports of goods includes change in the economic ownership of goods from non-residents to residents of the compiling economy, irrespective of physical movement of goods across national borders. Imports of services includes services provided by non-residents to residents. This indicator is expressed in current prices

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Findings and Discussion

The study employs annual time series data on GDP per capita, imports, and exports from the year 1995 to 2023.. Table 01 presents the descriptive statistics of the dataset. The distributions of GDP, exports, and imports are approximately normal, exhibiting a slight positive skewness. The relatively high level of variation indicates substantial fluctuations across the observed periods or entities. No significant outliers or departures from normality are detected. Consequently, the data are deemed appropriate for further econometric analyses, such as regression or correlation analysis, given their approximate normal distribution.

Table 01 Descriptive Statistics

	GDP	EXPO	IMPO
Mean	2405.601	1.13E+10	1.51E+10
Median	2026.659	1.01E+10	1.52E+10
Maximum	4398.888	2.03E+10	2.68E+10
Minimum	741.8383	4.62E+09	5.98E+09
Std. Dev.	1433.288	5.14E+09	7.19E+09
Skewness	0.080598	0.250656	0.096108
Kurtosis	1.261824	1.594580	1.439775
Jarque-Bera	3.682082	2.690377	2.986093
Probability	0.158652	0.260491	0.224687
Sum	69762.44	3.28E+11	4.38E+11
Sum Sq. Dev.	57520812	7.39E+20	1.45E+21

The mean GDP, exports, and imports indicate a general trend of economic expansion, with increasing trade volumes likely contributing to GDP growth (Figure 01). The higher variation in imports compared to exports may reflect higher sensitivity of imports to domestic demand and currency fluctuations. Export-led growth theory suggests that increasing exports boosts GDP by expanding production and improving efficiency through international competition and innovation. In Sri Lanka, export earnings (especially from textiles, tea, and remittances from service exports) contribute significantly to national

income.

Figure 01: Trend of import, Export, and GDP per capita in Sri Lanka

Table 02 presents the correlation coefficients among GDP, exports (EXPO), and imports (IMPO). The results indicate a strong positive correlation among all variables. Specifically, GDP is highly correlated with exports ($r = 0.9733$) and imports ($r = 0.9749$), while exports and imports also exhibit a very strong positive association ($r = 0.9750$). These coefficients, all approaching 1, suggest that increases in exports and imports are closely associated with increases in GDP. This implies that the economic growth represented by GDP is strongly linked to the performance of external trade. The high degree of inter-correlation among exports and imports further indicates that these variables tend to move together, possibly due to their mutual dependence in open economic activities. Overall, the results suggest a highly integrated relationship between GDP, exports, and imports, highlighting the significance of international trade in driving economic performance.

Table 02 Correlation

	GDP	EXPO	IMPO
GDP	1	0.9732	0.9749
EXPO	0.9732	1	0.9749
IMPO	0.9749	0.9749	1

Table 03 shows the regression results. The empirical results of the log-linear regression model provide compelling evidence of a strong and statistically significant relationship between gross domestic product (GDP), exports, and imports over the period 1995–2023. The estimated equation indicates that both exports (LNEXPO) and imports (LNIMPO) exert positive influences on economic growth, with respective elasticities of 0.56 and 0.80. This implies that, holding other factors constant, a 1% increase in exports leads to approximately a 0.56% rise in GDP, while a 1% increase in imports results in about a 0.80% increase in GDP. The relatively higher elasticity of imports suggests that imported goods, particularly capital equipment, intermediate inputs, and technology, play a more substantial role in driving production efficiency and overall economic expansion.

Table 01: Results of the Regression

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
LNEXPO	0.560125	0.286819	1.952888	0.0617
LNIMPO	0.797001	0.261942	3.042663	0.0053
C	-23.91513	1.185047	-20.18075	0.0000
R-squared	0.971145	Mean dependent var		7.570995
Adjusted R-squared	0.968925	S.D. dependent var		0.700667
S.E. of regression	0.123514	Akaike info criterion		-1.247230
Sum squared resid	0.396647	Schwarz criterion		-1.105786
Log likelihood	21.08484	Hannan-Quinn criter.		-1.202931
F-statistic	437.5258	Durbin-Watson stat		1.234142
Prob(F-statistic)	0.000000			

Source: Computed from the collected data

Regression Model

$$\ln(\text{GDP}) = -23.915 + 0.560\ln(\text{EXPO}) + 0.797\ln(\text{IMPO})$$

The explanatory power of the model is exceptionally high, as reflected by the R-squared value of 0.971. This indicates that nearly 97% of the variation in GDP can be explained by fluctuations in exports and imports. Such a strong fit underscores the vital role of international trade in shaping the economic performance of the country. The F-statistic (437.5) is significant at the 1% level, further confirming the joint explanatory strength of the independent variables. In other words, trade variables collectively have a substantial and statistically significant effect on economic growth. These results align with the trade-led growth hypothesis, which posits that openness to international trade enhances productivity, promotes competition, and fosters innovation key elements for sustained economic development.

From an economic perspective, the positive and significant coefficient for exports supports the idea that export expansion can stimulate domestic output by creating external demand for local goods and services. Export growth often encourages domestic industries to enhance efficiency, improve product quality, and adopt advanced technologies to remain competitive in global markets. Moreover, export earnings generate the foreign exchange needed to finance essential imports such as machinery, raw materials, and energy resources. In this regard, export-led strategies have been widely regarded as effective mechanisms for accelerating industrialisation and economic diversification, particularly in developing and emerging economies.

Interestingly, the coefficient for imports is not only positive but also more statistically significant and larger in magnitude than that of exports. This finding indicates that import activities are an equally, if

not more, crucial driver of economic growth. Imports often embody advanced technology, capital goods, and intermediate products that enhance domestic production capabilities. For many developing economies, the importation of high-quality inputs and machinery is essential to increase productivity and competitiveness. Therefore, while excessive reliance on imports can create trade deficits, the results here suggest that productive imports may have a complementary relationship with domestic output, stimulating GDP growth through technology diffusion and improved production processes.

The diagnostic statistics further reinforce the reliability of the model. The Jarque–Bera test reveals that residuals are approximately normally distributed ($p = 0.354$), confirming the validity of the ordinary least squares (OLS) assumptions. Although the Durbin–Watson statistic (1.234) indicates mild positive autocorrelation, the extent is not severe enough to undermine the model’s credibility. However, the condition number (1.71×10^3) suggests the presence of multicollinearity, likely due to the close interdependence between exports and imports an expected outcome in open economies where import and export activities are highly intertwined. For instance, imported raw materials or components may be used in the production of exportable goods, leading to a strong positive correlation between these two trade variables.

Overall, the regression results emphasize that economic growth during the study period has been largely trade-driven. The evidence supports the assertion that greater integration into global markets, through both exports and imports, has contributed significantly to output expansion. Policymakers should therefore aim to maintain a balanced trade policy that not only encourages export diversification but also ensures the efficient importation of capital and intermediate goods necessary for domestic industries. In particular, fostering policies that enhance export competitiveness, improve infrastructure, and strengthen industrial linkages between imports and local production could further amplify the growth benefits of trade openness.

Conclusion:

In conclusion, the findings demonstrate that trade liberalization and openness have played a pivotal role in driving GDP growth, affirming the empirical validity of the trade–growth nexus. While exports contribute to income generation and employment creation, imports support technological advancement and capital accumulation. The positive interaction between these two components indicates that sustained economic growth is best achieved through policies that simultaneously promote export expansion and the strategic utilization of imports to strengthen domestic production capacity. Future research could extend this analysis by incorporating additional macroeconomic variables such as foreign direct investment, exchange rate stability, and government expenditure to gain a more comprehensive understanding of the determinants of economic growth. In the case of Sri Lanka, exports and GDP per capita exhibit a parallel upward trend; however, imports have increased at a faster pace than exports, resulting in a persistent trade deficit. This pattern suggests an export-constrained growth model, where

the country's per capita income growth depends on effectively balancing trade by enhancing export performance while curbing non-essential imports.

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